

Recruitment and Selection in MSME Organizations with Special Reference to Andhra Pradesh

Mulaka Lakshmi Priya*, Janamala Krishnam Raju#, Kadimpalli-Rajubabu##

*Research Scholar, DCMS, Andhra University,

#Assistant Professor, Adikavi Nannaya University Campus, Tadepalligudem,

##Research Scholar, DCMS, Andhra University

priya.mulaka@gmail.com, kr.research@yahoo.com, [krebau689@gmail.com](mailto:krbau689@gmail.com)

Abstract

The skillful Human Resource Management of employees and their contribution to organization future prosperity. Effective recruitment and selection of employees are part of the employment relationship and can enhance work performance and contribute to business success. Micro Small Medium Enterprises' are one of the key drivers behind India's economic growth story. This sector, comprising of manufacturing, infrastructure, service industry, food processing, packaging, chemicals, and IT, has emerged as the most vibrant and dynamic engine of growth of Indian economy over the past few decades.

These self-funded proprietary firms, private co-operatives, private self-help groups, Khadi, and Village and Coir industries not only provide huge employment opportunities but also ensure regional balance by taking industrialization to rural and backward areas of about 20% of MSMEs operate out of rural & backward areas. In this context the researcher intends to study the practices and perspectives of recruitment and selection process opted by MSME organizations.

The main research objectives were to understand the variables and dynamics of the recruitment and selection process. The quantitative exploratory research was utilized to examine the recruitment and selection activities in MSME organizations in rural and urban areas of Andhra Pradesh. Descriptive statistics and factor analysis were used to derive the statistical significance of the hypothesis.

Keywords: Recruitment, Selection, Factor Analysis and MSME's.

1. Introduction

Human resource management is the essential function of organizations. Among the HR practises recruitment is the basic function where employees are entry into the organizations. Recruitment is the process of searching prospective employees. Selection is the process of choosing an appropriate candidate among the job applicants. Selection process starts after the completion of the recruitment process. Recruitment is the positive aspect whereas selection is the negative aspect of HR practises. Many of the researchers say that recruitment and selection policies should be ethical for the organizations in order to sustain in the competitive environment.

Recruitment is the first step then after selection and placement comes in the employment process. Employers aim is to choose an appropriate candidate suitable for that particular job. Recruitment is the activity done by the HR's in many organizations. The recruitment process differs from one organization to others. Recruitment is the process of attracting the candidates and making them to apply for the job.

Recruitment process followed at many Indian organizations is by framing the recruitment policy and then making the policy into action. Sources of the traditional recruitment are by employee referrals, transfers and promotions, walk-in and by the advertisements. In the modern economy the recruitment process was drastically changed with the entry of social media. Many organizations are following the online recruiting methods for attracting the

prospective employees. There are many factors that affect recruitment process like organization culture, working hours, facilities, salary, welfare, brand image, good will, location and etc.

Selection is the second step in the in the process of man power planning. Selection is the process of choosing the appropriate candidate which matches the candidate skills and the job requirements. Selection process will be lengthy for large organizations and will be wider for manufacturing organizations and it differs from one industry to other. Selection means dividing the total job applicants into two classes as selected and not selected. The selection process followed in many MSME's was the selection procedure of scientific selection procedure. There are many factors that are to be considered while selecting a candidate those are like group discussions, employment background, referral background, interviews, medical tests and etc.

MSME's: Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises, in accordance with the provision of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises Development (MSMED) Act, 2006 the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) are classified in two Classes:

1. Manufacturing Enterprises: The enterprises engaged in the manufacture or production of goods pertaining to any industry specified in the first schedule to the industries (Development and regulation) Act, 1951) or employing plant and machinery in the process of value addition to the final product having a distinct name or character or use. The Manufacturing Enterprise is defined in terms of investment in Plant & Machinery.

2. Service Enterprises: The enterprises engaged in providing or rendering of services and are defined in terms of investment in equipment.

Manufacturing Sector	
Enterprises	Investment in plant & machinery
Micro Enterprises	Does not exceed twenty five lakh rupees
Small Enterprises	More than twenty five lakh rupees but does not exceed five crore rupees
Medium Enterprises	More than five crore rupees but does not exceed ten crore rupees
Service Sector	
Enterprises	Investment in equipment's
Micro Enterprises	Does not exceed ten lakh rupees:
Small Enterprises	More than ten lakh rupees but does not exceed two crore rupees
Medium Enterprises	More than two crore rupees but does not exceed five crore rupees

Source: Government of India.

2. Objectives of the Study

The following are the research objectives of the study

- To study the various factors affecting while recruiting employees in MSME's
- To study the extension of several usage methods in staff selection in MSME's

3. Review of literature

M.Manonmani(2012) “The author has covered rural, urban and aggregate industries of India to examine linkage between wage and Productivity, it concluded that in rural industry that there is strong association of wage rate and labor productivity, in urban industries there is positive and statistically significant association between wage rate and labor productivity”

Sonal sisodia and Nimit Chowdhary (2012) It can be inferred that illustration in recruitment advertisement of service organization of service organization creates tangible representation and challenge the application to presume the intended significance of the illustrative appeal. Service employers should use visual communication to initiative relationship with prospective employees.

Mir Mohammed Nurul Absar (2012) states that Recruitment and selection is one the most important functions of human resource management. The present study aims at exploring differences and similarities between the public and private sector manufacturing firm of Bangladesh with respect to recruitment and selection practices, sources of recruitment and selection devices.

Ongori Henry and Temtime Z (2009) has to investigate the recruitment and selection practices of SMEs and suggest appropriate strategies on how to improve human resource management practices to enhance organizational performance. Recruitment and selection practices are the key factors to the entry point of human resource to any organization which also tends determine the success and sustainability of SMEs. These practices are said to encourage innovation, survival and growth of SMEs if taken serious by owner /mangers.

French ray and Rumbles sally (2010) says that the important role of recruitment and selection within the process of leading, managing and developing people. Recruitment and selection is pivotal in this regard in certain important respects.

As discussed by Jackson et al. (2009), human resource management approaches in any business organization are developed to meet corporate objectives and materialization of strategic plans. The nature of recruitment and selection for a company that is pursuing HRM approach is influenced by the state of the labour market and their strength within it. Furthermore, it is necessary for such companies to monitor how the state of labour market connects with potential recruits via the projection of an image, which will have an effect on and reinforce applicant expectations.

4. Scope of the study

The present research is confined to study the recruitment and selection process followed at different MSME's in Andhra Pradesh. The study considers the recruitment and selection process followed by the organizations only.

5. Research Design

Research design is defined as the specification of methods and procedures for accruing the information needed. It is a plan of organization frame for doing the collection of data. Data which is required for the study is collected from the primary data source. Primary data was collected through survey method by distributing questionnaires to HR managers. Random sampling technique was employed to collect the data and HR managers of different companies were consulted out of which 324 respondents were provided the required data. Sample size for the study is 324.

S No	Organization Type	Total No of Companies	No Samples for considering for the study (10% of population)	Actual respondents
1	Micro Industries	1,620	162	135
2	Small Scale Industries	2,224	222	184
3	Medium Scale	110	11	5
Total		3,954	395	324

Source: <https://msme.gov.in>

The total number of companies established in Andhra Pradesh in the year 2017 was 3,954. For the research study the samples were taken 10 percent of the population, out of which 324 respondents were replied for the questionnaire. Collected data were analysed by using factor analysis.

6. Limitations of the study

The present research is confined to study the recruitment and selection process followed at different MSME's in Andhra Pradesh. The study considers the recruitment and selection process followed by the organizations only.

7. Data Analysis and Interpretation

In order derive the most influencing factors in the process of recruitment and selection factor analysis was employed.

Factor Analysis:

Research Objective 1: Various factors affecting while recruiting employees in MSME's:

Descriptive Statistics:

The first output from the analysis is a table of descriptive statistics for all the variables under investigation. Typically, the mean, standard deviation and number of respondents (N) who participated in the survey are given. Looking at the mean, one can conclude that Specific skills required is the most effective variable while recruiting staff in the organizations. It has the highest mean of 3.68.

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
Specific skills required	3.68	.737	324
Type of business	3.52	.727	324
Demand for labour	3.48	.902	324
Economic conditions	3.57	.885	324
Salary/wages package able to offer	3.44	.810	324
Business location	3.67	.786	324
Employment laws	3.59	.990	324
Unions	3.54	.898	324

The Correlation matrix:

The next output from the analysis is the correlation coefficient. A correlation matrix is simply a rectangular array of numbers which gives the correlation coefficients between a single variable and every other variable in the investigation. The correlation coefficient between a variable and itself is always 1, hence the principal diagonal of the correlation matrix contains 1's. The correlation coefficients above and below the principal diagonal are the same. The determinant of the correlation matrix is shown at the foot of the table below.

Variables	Specific skills required	Type of business	Demand for labour	Economic conditions	Salary/wages package available	Business location	Employment	Unions
Specific skills required	1							
Type of business	-0.092	1						
Demand for labour	0.273	0.004	1					
Economic conditions	-0.296	0.145	0.082	1				
Salary/wages package available	0.006	0.07	0.355	0.161	1			
Business location	0.094	-0.053	0.113	0.300	0.083	1		
Employment	0.273	0.161	0.32	-0.053	0.373	0.267	1	
Unions	0.294	0.055	0.192	0.159	0.124	0.41	0.273	1

a. Determinant = 312

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test:

It measures strength of the relationship among variables. The KMO measures the sampling adequacy which should be greater than 0.5 for a satisfactory to apply factor analysis. If any pair of variables has a value less than this considers dropping one of them from the analysis. The off-diagonal elements should all be very small (close to zero) in a good model. Looking at the table below, the KMO measure is 0.758. The general acceptance value to recommend factor analysis is 0.50 as minimum, values between 0.7-0.8 acceptable, and values above 0.9 are excellent for analysis.

Bartlett's test is another indication of the strength of the relationship among variables. This tests the null hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. An identity matrix is matrix in which all of the diagonal elements are 1 and all off diagonal elements are 0. From the same table, Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant That is, its associated probability is less than 0.05. In fact, it is actually 0.000, i.e. the significance level is small enough to reject the null hypothesis. This means that correlation matrix is not an identity matrix.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.758
	Approx. Chi-Square	372.366
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	28
	Sig.	.000

Communalities:

The next item from the output is a table of communalities which shows how much of the variance in the variables has been accounted for by the extracted factors. For instance over 76.3% of the variance in economic conditions while 72.5% of the variance for business location.

Communalities:

	Initial	Extraction
Specific skills required	1.000	.664
Type of business	1.000	.406
Demand for labour	1.000	.492
Economic conditions	1.000	.763
Salary/wages package able to offer	1.000	.598
Business location	1.000	.725
Employment laws	1.000	.608
Unions	1.000	.571

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Scree Plot:

The scree plot is a graph of the eigen values against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain. The point of interest is where the curve starts to flatten. It can be seen that the curve begins to flatten after factor 3, so only three factors have been retained.

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.249	28.115	28.115	2.249	28.115	28.115	1.808	22.602	22.602
2	1.385	17.315	45.43	1.385	17.315	45.43	1.638	20.478	43.08
3	1.193	14.909	60.339	1.193	14.909	60.339	1.381	17.259	60.339
4	0.954	11.93	72.268						
5	0.691	8.634	80.902						
6	0.598	7.476	88.378						
7	0.522	6.528	94.906						
8	0.407	5.094	100						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component (Factor) Matrix:

The table below shows the loadings of the eight variables on the three factors extracted. The higher the absolute value of the loading, the more the factor contributes to the variable. The gap on the table represent loadings that are less than 0.5, this makes reading the table easier. Here the researcher suppressed all loadings less than 0.5.

Component Matrix^a

Variables	Component		
	1	2	3
Specific skills required		-.640	
Type of business			
Demand for labour	.637		
Economic conditions		.827	
Salary/wages package able to offer	.548		.525
Business location	.610		-.542
Employment laws	.702		
Unions	.629		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a. 3 components extracted.

Rotated Component (Factor) Matrix:

The idea of rotation is to reduce the number factors on which the variables under investigation have high loadings. Rotation does not actually change anything but makes the interpretation of the analysis easier. Looking at the table below, it can observe that Demand for labour, Salary/wages package able to offer and Employment laws are loaded on Factor 1. Economic conditions, Business location and unions are located on Factor 2 and all the remaining variables are loaded on Factor 3.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

Variables	Component		
	1	2	3
Specific skills required			-.717
Type of business			.507
Demand for labour	.662		
Economic conditions		.514	.705
Salary/wages package able to offer	.737		
Business location		.846	
Employment laws	.744		
Unions		.715	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Research Objective 2: Extension of several usage methods in staff selection in MSME's:

Descriptive Statistics

The first output from the analysis is a table of descriptive statistics for all the variables under investigation. Typically, the mean, standard deviation and number of respondents (N) who participated in the survey are given. Looking at the mean, one can conclude that testing is the most effective variable while selection of staff in the organizations. It has the highest mean of 3.64.

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
Initial screening interview	3.50	.991	324
Background investigation/reference check	3.40	.983	324
Unstructured interview	3.25	1.056	324
Structured interview	3.23	1.116	324
Completing an application form	3.17	.985	324
Literacy test (reading/writing)	2.85	1.186	324
Group interview	3.43	.882	324
Testing	3.64	.845	324
Physical examination	3.59	.974	324
Stress interview	3.44	.967	324
Computer-assisted interview	3.52	1.009	324

The Correlation matrix:

The next output from the analysis is the correlation coefficient. A correlation matrix is simply a rectangular array of numbers which gives the correlation coefficients between a single variable and every other variable in the investigation. The correlation coefficient between a variable and itself is always 1, hence the principal diagonal of the correlation matrix contains 1's. The correlation coefficients above and below the principal diagonal are the same. The determinant of the correlation matrix is shown at the foot of the table below.

Correlation Matrix^a

Attributes	Initial screening interview	Background investigation /reference check	Unstructured interview	Structured interview	Completing an application form	Literacy test (reading/writing)	Group interview	testing	Physical examination	Stress interview	Computer-assisted interview
Initial screening interview	1										
Background investigation /reference check	0.382	1									
Unstructured interview	0.461	0.42	1								
Structured interview	0.046	0.111	-0.016	1							
Completing an application form	0.153	0.028	0.013	0.289	1						
Literacy test (reading/writing)	0.004	0.181	0.036	0.35	0.474	1					
Group interview	-0.088	-0.111	-0.107	-0.152	-0.113	-0.109	1				
testing	0.012	-0.015	-0.022	-0.059	0.025	-0.006	0.165	1			
Physical examination	0.009	-0.062	-0.058	-0.017	-0.092	-0.119	0.292	0.306	1		
Stress interview	-0.071	-0.016	-0.049	-0.069	-0.108	-0.049	0.224	0.372	0.351	1	
Computer-assisted interview	0.034	0.033	0.005	-0.007	-0.169	-0.074	0.373	0.155	0.455	0.207	1

a. Determinant = .155

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test:

It measures strength of the relationship among variables. The KMO measures the sampling adequacy which should be greater than 0.5 for a satisfactory to apply factor analysis. If any pair of variables have a value less than this considers dropping one of them from the analysis. The off-diagonal elements should all be very small (close to zero) in a good model. Looking at the table below, the KMO measure is 0.747. The general acceptance value to recommend factor analysis is 0.50 as minimum, values between 0.7-0.8 acceptable, and values above 0.9 are superb.

Bartlett's test is another indication of the strength of the relationship among variables. This tests the null hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. An identity matrix is matrix in which all of the diagonal elements are 1 and all off diagonal elements are 0. From the same table, Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant That is, its associated probability is less than 0.05. In fact, it is actually 0.000, i.e. the significance level is small enough to reject the null hypothesis. This means that correlation matrix is not an identity matrix.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.747
	Approx. Chi-Square	595.501
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	55
	Sig.	.000

Communalities:

The next item from the output is a table of communalities which shows how much of the variance in the variables has been accounted for by the extracted factors. For instance over 74.8% of the variance in computer assisted interview while 71.5% of the variance in testing.

Communalities

Variables	Initial	Extraction
Initial screening interview	1.000	.615
Background investigation/reference check	1.000	.577
Unstructured interview	1.000	.666
Structured interview	1.000	.548
Completing an application form	1.000	.608
Literacy test (reading/writing)	1.000	.659
Group interview	1.000	.487
testing	1.000	.715
Physical examination	1.000	.598
Stress interview	1.000	.612
Computer-assisted interview	1.000	.748

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Total Variance Explained:

The next item shows all the factors extractable from the analysis along with their eigenvalues, the percent of variance attributable to each factor, and the cumulative variance of the factor and the previous factors. Notice that the first factor accounts for 21.861% of the variance, the second 16.731%, the third 14.333% and the fourth is 9.189% remaining variables are less significant.

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.405	21.861	21.861	2.405	21.861	21.861	1.864	16.945	16.945
2	1.84	16.731	38.592	1.84	16.731	38.592	1.763	16.031	32.977
3	1.577	14.333	52.924	1.577	14.333	52.924	1.744	15.852	48.828
4	1.011	9.189	62.113	1.011	9.189	62.113	1.461	13.285	62.113
5	0.824	7.49	69.603						
6	0.758	6.888	76.491						
7	0.598	5.434	81.925						
8	0.588	5.346	87.271						
9	0.529	4.813	92.085						
10	0.472	4.294	96.379						
11	0.398	3.621	100						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Scree Plot:

The scree plot is a graph of the eigenvalues against all the factors. The graph is useful for determining how many factors to retain. The point of interest is where the curve starts to flatten. It can be seen that the curve begins to flatten between factors 3 and 4. Note also that factor 4 has an eigenvalue of greater than 1, so only four factors have been retained.

Eigenvalue: The standardized variance associate with a particular factor. The sum of the eigenvalues cannot exceed the number of items in the analysis, since each item contributes one to the sum of variances.

Component (Factor) Matrix:

The table below shows the loadings of the eleven variables on the four factors extracted. The higher the absolute value of the loading, the more the factor contributes to the variable. The gap on the table represent loadings that are less than 0.5, this makes analyzing the table easier. Here the researcher suppressed all loadings less than 0.5.

Component Matrix^a

Variables	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Initial screening interview		.661		
Background investigation /reference check		.642		
Unstructured interview		.626		
Structured interview			.553	
Completing an application form			.604	
Literacy test (reading/writing)			.644	
Group interview	.599			
testing				-.584
Physical examination	.634			
Stress interview	.549			
Computer-assisted interview	.558			.522

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a. 4 components extracted.

Rotated Component (Factor) Matrix:

The idea of rotation is to reduce the number factors on which the variables under investigation have high loadings. Rotation does not actually change anything but makes the interpretation of the analysis easier. Initial screening interview, Background investigation/reference check and unstructured interview loaded on Factor 1. Structured interview, Completing an application form and Literacy test (reading/writing) loaded on Factor 2. Group interview, Physical examination and Computer-assisted interview loaded on Factor 3 and all the remaining variables loaded on Factor 4. These factors can be used as variables for further analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

Variables	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Initial screening interview	.783			
Background investigation/reference check	.747			
Unstructured interview	.810			
Structured interview		.714		
Completing an application form		.747		
Literacy test (reading/writing)		.805		
Group interview			.661	
Testing				.841
Physical examination			.667	
Stress interview				.742
Computer-assisted interview			.859	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

8. Findings of the study

- The analysis carried out in the sample survey reveals that majority of the respondents agree the recruitment policy suffices to the recruitment of the company.
- Majority of the respondents are of the view that the recruitment policy helps you to recruit members with right skill set.
- The study reveals that respondents feel very good about the are sufficient to the efficiency of recruitment policy in terms of recruitment and selection process.
- In the process of recruitment, Specific skills required, Type of business and Demand for labour is the most influencing factors in the MSME organizations.
- Only three factors considered for the study.

➤ In the Selection process the factors, Initial screening interview, Background investigation/reference check, unstructured interview and structured interview are the most influencing factors.

Conclusion

Recruitment and selection process is getting very much importance these days in MSME organizations. It is very critical thing to evaluate the human resource. It is a systematic procedure that involves many activities. The process includes the step like HR planning attaining applicant and screening them. It is very important activity as it provides right place at right time. It is not easy not an easy task as organization future is depending on this activity, if suitable employees are selected which are beneficial to the MSME's. It is at safe side but if decision goes wrong it can be dangerous to the organization. So it is an activity for which human resource departments gets very much importance. Recruitment and selection procedure and its important also get changed as the organization changed.

References:

1. Absar, M. M. (2012). Recruitment & Selection Practices in Manufacturing Firms in Bangladesh. *The Indian Journal of Industrial Relations*, 47 (3), 436-448.
2. Amanda J. Daly, M. C. (2009). Preferences in recruitment and selection in a sample of Australian organizations. *International Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 9 (1), 581-593.
3. ANYIM, F. C. (2012). The role of human resource planning in recruitment and selection process. *British Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6 (2),45-58
4. Armstrong, C. P. (2006). Current Recruitment and Selection Practices: A National Survey of Fortune 1000 Firms. *North American journal of psychology*, 8 (3), 489-496.
5. Armstrong, C. P. (2006). Current Recruitment and Selection Practices: A National Survey of Fortune 1000 Firms. *North American Journal of Psychology*, 8 (3), 489-496.
6. Avinash S. Kapse, V. S. (2012). E- Recruitment. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 1 (4), 234-248
7. Bhattacharyya, S. J. (2012). Study of Perceived Recruitment Practices and their Relationships to Job Satisfaction. *Synergy*, 10 (1), 63-72.
8. Bibi Asia Naz, U. A. (2012). Factors Affecting the Teaching Faculty Recruitment/ Selection in Factors Affecting the Teaching Faculty Recruitment/Selection in. *LANGUAGE IN INDIA*, 12 (3), 34-43.
9. Bouzguenda, K. (2013). Towards a Global Framework of Recruitment Practices: The Effect of Culture Applied to Tunisian Context. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5 (7), 25-32.
10. Briggs, B. R. (2007). Problems of recruitment in civil service: case of the Nigerian civil service. *African Journal of Business Management*, 1 (6), 142-153.
11. Chowdhary, S. S. (2013). Use of illustrations in recruitment advertising. *Journal of Services Research*, 12 (2), 24- 36.
12. Clark, P. recruitment and selection practices in a selected organization. *Journal of Management Practice*, 4 (1), 166 - 167.
13. Cornelius J. Ko nig, U.-C. K. (2010). Reasons for Being Selective When Choosing Personnel Selection Procedures. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 18 (27), 18-27.
14. Corte, F. L. (2008). Development and test of a model of external organizational commitment in human resources outsourcing. *Human Resource Management*, 47 (3), 559-579.
15. Czerniawska, F. (2005). The new business consulting landscape. *Issues and Trends*, 16 (4), 1-8.
16. Jahan, M. (2012). Recruitment and Selection Process in Bangladesh Civil Service: A Critical Overview. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 2 (5), 85-92
17. Leat, Y.-R. H. (2000). A study of HRM and recruitment and selection policies and practices in Taiwan. *International journal of HRM*, 11 (2), 413-435.
18. Madan, R. (2012). Recruitment and selection practices across cultures. *International journal of research in commerce and management*, 3 (1), 87-93.
19. Malcolm Martin, F. W. (2010). Recruitment and selection. *Human Resource Practice*, 3 (2), 110-144.
20. Omolo, R. D. (2012). Effect of Recruitment and Selection of Employees on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Kisumu Municipality, Kenya. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 2 (3), 81- 98
21. Silvestri, A. O. (2008). Recruitment and selection services: Efficiency and competitive reasons in the outsourcing of HR practices. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19 (2), 372-391.